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Abstract: Comprehensive final report providing an overview of the training materials collected and developed within the SSHOC project, also detailing the adopted methodology with respect to the collection of existing materials as well as the creation of new ones. Separate sections concentrate on the hosting and the integration with the SSH Open Marketplace.

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Executive Summary

This report describes the results of task 6.3 “Empowering Users: Training Materials and Online Learning Paths” of the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud project funded by the European Commission under Grant #823782. In line with the FAIR principles, these tasks focused on three aspects: a) **inventorising** the existing resources to foster their **findability**; b) means to **create** training material in a way maximizing **reuse**; b) ensuring the long-term availability of the information gathered.

In order to **inventorise** the landscape and to foster the findability of existing resources, an application has been developed in the initial project phase, which has served as means for collective curation of the information about existing training material, as well as a discovery platform for the community, the Training Discovery Toolkit. The manual inventorisation in collaboration with task 6.4 “Building Expertise: the SSHOC Training Network” pursued two perspectives: one giving a broad overview of the landscape, concentrating on potential sources for training materials relevant for the SSH community underpinned by a sample set of training materials featured in these sources; the other stemming from the cooperation with task 6.4 accordingly more focused on training materials specifically usable by trainers in their educational measures. The details of the train-the-trainer approach and the SSH Training Community are given in two related project reports, deliverable 6.11 *SSHOC train-the-trainer toolkit (final)*, and deliverable 6.13 *Report on the SSHOC Training network (updated version)*.

The basic methodology and the initial statistics regarding the collection of information have been described in *D6.7 Inventory of training materials*. This deliverable offers an update about the information collected in this catalogue.

In this task, the team adopted a broad understanding of the concept “training materials” as resources usable for knowledge sharing, ranging from traditional e-learning modules employed in university curricula, through presentations and videos accompanying workshops on selected topics, to tutorials describing the use of a specific tool, or workflows detailing a specific procedure, down to resources, which on its own are not considered as training materials, but could be beneficially integrated into these, especially interactive resources like data notebooks or games. Another dimension considered was the intended audiences, especially aiming to distinguish between resources that can be used directly and independently by learners, as opposed to “training materials” (re-)usable by trainers in their teaching procedures. While learning resources were not generally excluded, the focus was on “training materials”, in line with the goals of SSHOC task 6.4.

Another aspect covered by this task was the **creation of new training materials**. While there are meanwhile numerous institutional e-learning platforms and many ways to create and share traditional training material like slides, or videos, in exchange with the stakeholders a need was identified to be able to author and publish training material in an open, collaborative, and reusable way. To answer this need, task 6.3 in tight collaboration with an editorial team of an existing platform for training materials has developed a novel technical solution for creating, editing, and publishing training materials. This solution

can be reused as a service run by one of the RIs (DARIAH-campus), or by hosting a dedicated instance of the code, which is available open source.

A major challenge looking ahead is the question of **sustainability** and reusability of the training materials catalogued and created within SSHOC. Only if the resources stay available and the catalogue is kept up to date, it can become a useful resource for the community in the long run. This entails **continuous curation**, both by reviewing the validity of the existing information and collecting new. Given the conceptual overlap, it is recommended to align the curation efforts with those of the SSH Open Marketplace, developed in SSHOC Work Package 7, making use of the community and a dedicated editorial team to curate the catalogue of training materials. The report details the mechanism of integration of the information gathered in T6.3 into the SSH Open Marketplace, as well as EOSC at large. It will also be important to align with the corresponding curation activities of the individual research infrastructures, and their community-specific efforts in knowledge sharing.

By bringing together the different facets of training materials in an infrastructural project such as SSHOC, this report provides an overview of the topics for SSH learners and trainers, and suggests appropriate sustainable technical solutions for creation, and publication, and thus findability, and reusability.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACDH-CH	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CMS	Content Management System
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
MP	(SSH Open) Marketplace
TDT	SSH Training Discovery Toolkit
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	SSH Open Cloud

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1. Introduction

The goal of task 6.3 “Empowering Users: Training Materials and Online Learning Paths” was primarily to provide an overview and to collect existing training materials in the area of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), as well as to support the creation of training materials within the SSHOC project. The task of inventoring was summarized in a previous deliverable *D6.7 Inventory of training materials*¹. An update of the state of affairs is given in section 2 Landscape which details how the initial inventory has been reused for train-the-trainer purposes and in section 3 Metadata that depicts how SSHOC training materials metadata have been developed in relation to other existing schemas.

Another part of the work of task 6.3 concentrated on devising a new technical system, which supports the creation of new training materials as described in section 4.

Finally, with respect to the sustainability and longevity of the efforts, the task operated in close coordination with the WP7, developing the SSH Open Marketplace², a discovery platform for resources relevant for SSH research, including training material. Details of this collaboration are described in section 5.

2. Landscape

In the initial phase of the project, an application has been developed, which is serving as a catalogue or inventory of SSH relevant training materials. The application and its initial data population were described in D6.7. In the further course of the project it was decided, in collaboration with task 6.4 “Building Expertise: the SSHOC Training Network”, to further refine the application to serve especially as a catalogue of training material which can be used by trainers - the focus of task 6.4 - for their teaching purposes.

All in all, task 6.3 operated in a very dynamic and heterogeneous environment, as illustrated in figure 1. On the one hand, there is a vast space of existing training materials of various kinds scattered across a large number of platforms, some of them specific to SSH, others very general in scope, however still containing training materials relevant for SSH. On the other hand, training materials have been created also in the context of the SSHOC project, the specific input coming from individual work packages, channelled by the work of the other tasks of WP6, especially to support a series of training events. These materials were made available via dedicated collections in Zenodo and YouTube and catalogued from the training area of the main project website³.

¹ Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, & Laure Barbot. (2019). SSHOC D6.7 Inventory of existing learning materials (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558297> [22.11.2021]

² SSH Open Marketplace: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/> [24.11.2021]

³ Training section on the SSHOC project website: <https://sshopencloud.eu/training> [22.11.2021]

Fig. 1: SSHOC training materials environment

2.1 Collecting existing material: the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT)⁴ is meant to support trainers, part of the trainers' network built up in WP6. It was developed in T6.3 in the initial phase of the project to compile an inventory of training materials relevant for SSH as well as the sources, i.e. platforms hosting these materials. It was subsequently adopted by T6.4 to specifically collect information about training material usable by trainers of the SSH domain for their educational measures, especially those provided by the research infrastructures of the SSH cluster CESSDA, CLARIN and DARIAH. Collecting and curating the training material metadata is an ongoing joint task in T6.3 and T6.4. The TDT offers the technical framework for content management and for accessing and searching this extensive and continuously growing collection.

The methodology of the data collection, the technical implementation of the inventory, as well as the initial statistics are detailed in deliverable D6.7. Here is to summarize and reiterate the methodological approach: in an iterative manual curation process involving the members of the task team, existing sources, i.e. platforms, with training materials have been identified, and gathered into a shared spreadsheet. In this process, also the fields for describing the sources were agreed upon. In parallel, a

⁴ SSH Training Discovery Toolkit: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/>

simple custom application was developed, into which this initial list of sources, including the descriptive properties was imported. In a dedicated curation sprint for each of the sources an illustrative sample of items has been manually entered, again including a set of descriptive properties. The values for these properties were either taken over directly from the sources or were based on a controlled vocabulary agreed upon by the curation team. The controlled vocabularies are crucial for systemizing the data collection and making it useful for discovery.

In the following paragraphs, basic descriptive statistics of the data in the TDT are presented, by way of an update to the initial numbers presented in the deliverable D6.7.

There are currently⁵ 300 entries recorded in the TDT. This comprises 86 sources and 214 items. A source is an online platform or application, where one or more training material is stored and accessible. An item is a specific training material available at a source. As part of the descriptive metadata, sources are usually connected to one or more organisations responsible for providing the given platform; the list of collected organisations includes 106 organisations. The five organisations with the most connected sources are listed in Table 1.

Name of organisation	Number of connected sources
CLARIN ERIC	6
DARIAH ERIC	6
Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	5
GESIS – Leibniz-Institute for the Social Sciences	5
The Carpentries	4

Table 1: Organisations with the most connected sources in the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

Given the richness of existing training resources, it was not feasible - and also not relevant within the SSHOC scope - to provide a comprehensive catalogue of all the items featured in these sources. Rather the intention was to offer an overview by way of an exemplary sample. Thus while the list of sources is exhaustive for the scope in question, on the level of individual items, only a few from each source have been picked and described in a manual curation process to get a better understanding of what training material is to be expected from a source (in terms of training material type and description - metadata - for these training materials). Nevertheless, the sources with the most items do give a good overview and clear guidance on the major players that offer specialised training material for the SSH community (see Table 2).

⁵ Statistics created on 23.11.2021.

Name of source	Number of registered items
CLARIN Resource Families	17
CLARIN Depositing Services	13
DARIAH-CAMPUS	12
UK Data Service: Manage Data	9
CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide	8
OpenAIRE Training and Support	8
FOSTER Open Sciences: Courses	7
PARTHENOS Project	7
SERISS Project	7
EHRI Training	6

Table 2: Major sources based on the number of registered items in the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

One important categorisation of the TDT content is the assignment of topic tags to items, which was done by curators. These tags support the browsing and grouping of training material items. The topic tags are organised in a controlled vocabulary created through manual consolidation and harmonisation of the broad range of keywords collected from the various sources. The list of topic tags currently includes 16 concepts (see Table 3) and is open for new concepts if deemed relevant by the moderators. It expresses important clusters of training topics: data creation, data management, using tools and programming, didactics, and training methods. The statistics show a prevalence of topics like “research data management”, “FAIR data”, and “open science”. This is probably not only because of the importance of these topics but also due to the focus of the train-the-trainer program of WP6/T6.4.

There is also a rich variety of training material on different aspects of data creation, expressed in the topic tags “Survey data”, “Data”, “Metadata”, “Spatial data” and partly “Text encoding and TEI”. Furthermore, thanks to the topic tags it is potentially possible to combine training material on data creation with training material on data management, thus constructing a meaningful learning path.

Topic tag	Number of items
Research data management/FAIR data	131
Open Science	45

Text encoding and TEI	38
Didactics	26
Quantitative analysis	19
Data visualization	14
Survey data	13
Copyright	13
Data	13
Metadata	12
Python/Jupyter	10
Digital edition	9
Programming with R	8
GIT	6
Citizen science	5
Spatial data	5

Table 3: Most popular topic tags in the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

The popularity of the topics seems to correlate with the indication of the intended audience. The TDT data model allows indicating the envisaged audience for each training material, relying on a controlled vocabulary. Analyzing this category/dimension (see Table 4) suggests that most training materials represented in the catalogue are oriented directly to researchers, followed by items usable by trainers. This seems to correlate well, with the strong focus on the topic “data management”, similarly to the cluster on data creation correlating to the well-represented audience of “data creators”.

It is also to be noted that materials tagged for students may also be suitable for trainers. A clear distinction between “training materials” (materials that can be reused by trainers to create new materials or directly for teaching) and “learning materials” (materials ready to be used by students to learn a new topic) is not always possible.

Audience tag	Assigned number of items
Researcher	231
Trainer	167
Data creator	146
Student	144
Data steward	143
Data provider	103
Service provider	74
Public	56

Table 4: Intended audience of the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit items

Another dimension describing the training materials is the disciplines they pertain to (see Table 5). A large portion of the material is not considered domain-specific (expressed in the most common tag “all/multiple disciplines”). Not very surprising, but confirming the scope of the SSHOC project, is the fact that social sciences and digital humanities are the second- and third-most applied discipline tags. The long tail are mostly subdisciplines of SSH, e.g. corpus linguistics or political sciences. Altogether, these statistics of the use of discipline tags display nicely the SSH focus of the TDT.

Discipline tag	Assigned number of items
All/multiple disciplines	70
Social Sciences	51
Digital humanities	44
History	19
Computational Linguistics	18
Humanities	18
Corpus Linguistics	14
Cultural heritage and museology	8

Art and art history	7
Environmental Research	7
Linguistics	7
Information sciences	6
Library and information sciences	6

Table 5: Most popular discipline tags in the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

Finally, there is information/statistics regarding the type of training material (see Table 6). The format of the training material is based on a controlled vocabulary that is manually assigned by curators to items added to the TDT. The statistics show a wide variety of formats in use, unsurprisingly dominated by courses, e-learning modules and units or lessons of such courses followed by videos, webinars, and slides. Materials in the tools present also less common types, which are worth further investigation: These are text-based material like blog entries, reports and books, and even more so interactive formats like games, data notebooks, checklists or demos. While these are often not directly usable for training, they can be reused by trainers to be included, e.g., as an assignment in a course. Data notebooks are ideal means for hands-on interactive learning of coding skills, which could accompany, e.g., courses on data curation.

It also needs to be noted that any such categorisation is just an approximation, without clear-cut boundaries and some materials may fit into multiple categories. Nevertheless, it offers a rough overview and guidance to the users.

The two categories “workshops” and “events” require further attention, given that strictly speaking, these aren’t training materials. While the line between the materials and the events to which they pertain is somewhat blurry in the digital representation, the training event itself offers an important structuring dimension and contextual information, to wrap the related information around, like the webpage informing about the event, its program/agenda, a potential recording, or the slides presented at the event. This contextualized representation of the information is information-rich and thus beneficial for the users.

Format tags	Assigned number of items
Unit/Lesson	67
E-learning module	64
Video	63
Webinar	50

Slides	47
Course	40
Game	35
Blog	33
Workshop	29
Events	24
Report	18
Book	15
Checklist	14
Data Notebook (jupyter)	12
Demo	6

Table 6: Training materials format of the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit items

The numbers make it quite clear that the curation effort of the TDT team led to high-quality metadata that helps to get a very detailed picture of the training material landscape in the SSH domain. It shows not only the rich variety of different formats, involved disciplines, intended audiences, and topics of the many training material items but also possible connections between them. At the same time, by answering the question, which topics (or which audiences) may be underrepresented in the existing materials, it allows us to identify potential gaps, informing potential decisions (within RIs or dedicated projects) on creating new materials.

Another take-away/lesson to be learned is the importance of meaningful controlled vocabularies. By offering a structure they support and simplify the work of the curators, and at the same time help to raise the quality of the metadata. Well-curated vocabularies are necessary precondition/prerequisite for discoverability/findability of training material. The statistics shown in this subchapter exemplary refer to vocabularies used in the TDT e.g., audiences, disciplines.

Well maintained vocabularies are also necessary for mapping to other platforms, e.g., the SSH Open Marketplace. It was interesting to discover that for many of the data fields of the TDT no community-agreed vocabularies are in place. Therefore, most vocabularies were built up within the development of the TDT. They are in evaluation and are discussed within the SSHOC project as long as new data is generated. Some work still needs to be invested in the selection and definition of vocabulary terms, which is connected with data cleaning by curators. Additionally, the feedback of data editors is especially

valuable for finishing this task. The current state of the TDT vocabularies is very well accepted by the users and the statistics presented here already show the benefit of well-expressed vocabularies. There is also a strong exchange between work packages within the SSHOC project and with other projects on aligning vocabulary development efforts. Of course, the final versions of the vocabularies are to be published on dedicated vocabulary servers for further re-use, e.g., for the SSH Open Marketplace.

2.2 Creating new material: the SSHOC Training resources

Knowledge sharing conveyed through dedicated training events accompanied by corresponding training material is considered a cornerstone of infrastructural projects, as the means to make the newly introduced methods and tools known to the potential audiences, and also to support the practice of working with data in general. In the SSHOC project, this understanding was expressed in the establishment of a dedicated work package 6 *Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise*, which concentrated on understanding the communities and their needs and offering them training events and materials. Given the wide scope of topics covered in an infrastructural project such as SSHOC, it was understood that it cannot be the sole task of the WP team to generate and prepare materials for identified needs, but rather it should act as a coordinating instance or a channel, gathering and conveying the topic-specific information from the other work packages to the respective audiences, in collaboration with the respective WP teams.

As the primary channel for publishing the outputs (the events description and the related materials), a dedicated set of pages on the SSHOC website, SSHOC Training resources⁶, has been introduced. Despite the difficulties arising from the pandemic situation, a total of 28 (mostly online) events have been conducted (considering the time frame until the writing of this deliverable). However, some of them were not training events in the strict sense (like awareness raising events). The typical mode for the online presentation of the training events was a dedicated page on the website (see Figure 2), announcing the event, pointing to a video recording of the event (hosted on the SSHOC-channel on YouTube⁷) and the training materials presented, mostly in form of presentation slides published as part of the dedicated SSHOC-community collection on Zenodo⁸.

⁶ Training events on SSHOC website: <https://sshopencloud.eu/training/training-events> [23.11.2021]

⁷ SSHOC Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCw-mY8v84yeHW2z4KG3ZLtA/> [23.11.2021]

⁸ SSHOC Zenodo Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sshoc/?page=1&size=20> [23.11.2021]

SSHOC Workshop: Providing canonical training materials for secure data facility professionals

[Home](#) / [Events](#) / SSHOC Workshop: Providing canonical training materials for secure data facility professionals

SSHOC Workshop: Providing canonical training materials for secure data facility professionals

21 September, 14:30-16:30 (CEST)

Date: 21 September 2021 - 14:30 to 16:30
Location: Online

News

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Workshop Notes: SSHOC Archaeological Case Study - The Roman Theatre in Catania from Survey to Interactive 4D Visualisation
A dedicated interdisciplinary community within the SSHOC project is working...

Fig 2: Example of a training event announcement page on the SSHOC website - screenshot

In order to ensure the findability of these project outcomes, it is foreseen to integrate information about them as part of the SSH Open Marketplace, one of the central discovery platforms for SSH related resources in the context of EOSC. Details of the integration are described in the dedicated section 5.

Next to the events and the materials, the experts have been recognized as crucial actors and multipliers in the task of knowledge sharing. Task 6.4 was dedicated to establishing and maintaining a training community⁹, i.e., a group of trainers sharing their experience on and means of knowledge sharing. Task 6.3 has been supporting this effort by customizing the Training Discovery Toolkit, described in the previous section, to the specific needs of this community, e.g., allowing the trainers to flag and search for training materials, especially useful in the “train the trainers” situations.

⁹ SSHOC training community: <https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-training-community> [23.11.2021]

3. Metadata - description of training materials

A critical prerequisite for the discoverability of training materials or resources, in general, is the availability of widely understandable metadata or description of the resources.

The data model of TDT was specifically created to cover the needs for describing resources in the context of T6.3 training material inventory and the further use in T6.4. It is explained and described in the deliverable D6.7. To raise the search engine optimisation (SEO) scores and to support interoperability, it was decided to map the TDT data model to applicable Schema.org¹⁰ schemas, a combination of CreativeWork and LearningResource¹¹. This is an ongoing effort and includes mappings to further data models describing training material. The Schema.org mapping is applied to the fields of the TDT content (as additional attributes on the level of the HTML tags) as well as an API endpoint to get an export of a training material source or item in JSON-LD format adhering to the Schema.org schema. Deliverable D6.11 *SSHOC train-the-trainer toolkit (final)* by task 6.4 describes the mapping process and the experiences made in detail. The work on the mappings to Schema.org and other data models offered additional confirmation that the TDT data model is appropriate for describing training material in sufficient detail, compatible with corresponding efforts in this area, which is an important prerequisite to foster the sharing of the information on training material collected in TDT in line with the FAIR principles.

¹⁰ Schema.org: <https://schema.org/> [22.11.2021]

¹¹ Schema LearningResource: <https://schema.org/LearningResource> [22.11.2021]

4. Innovative solution for the creation of training materials

To support the creation of training materials beyond “talking head” videos and presentation slides, the team of task 6.3 developed a novel technical solution based on input from a team responsible for production of training materials within the context of one of the ERIC of the RI-cluster (DARIAH). .

In general, one can discern three modes of creation and presentation of training materials. First, there are e-learning platforms like moodle, second presentation slides, optionally accompanied by a video recording of the speaker. The third, increasingly popular option is to create the training material using a simple format like markdown¹², to maintain the material openly through a git-based repository and to publish it on a website, by means of rendering the material into static HTML pages. The advantage of the third approach is its radical openness, the raw material being readily available, especially relevant in the reviewing process. A popular example of this approach in Digital Humanities is the website Programming Historian¹³. The downside of this approach is the rather cumbersome authoring mechanism, where the authors are forced to deal with a git repository and to write the material in plain text format like markdown, which does not lend itself well, for more complex formatting. Even though all this can be remedied by appropriate client text editors (such as Sublime¹⁴, Atom¹⁵ or Notepad++¹⁶ for example), offering syntax-support and an on-the-fly rendering of the markdown-formatted text, as well as integration with git, this still poses a major obstacle or barrier to entry for new contributors.

Therefore, based on a requirements specification, which was a compilation of multiple user feedback to the original version of DARIAH-Campus, the team developed a new solution, which combines the ease of authoring of a content management system (CMS), with the openness of a git-based approach. The solution was test-used by two teams with around seven users altogether and fine-tuned in a series of feedback iterations. The underlying technology was NetlifyCMS¹⁷, a framework that allows operating a full-fledged CMS including a publication workflow, as well as a rich-text editor, transparently on top of a git repository. This means that the authors can create and edit their training material directly via a CMS, never needing to deal with git or markdown at all, thus offering a far easier and more intuitive way to submit content. At the same time, persons attuned to a git-based workflow can work, even on the same material, in the traditional way, i.e., by cloning the git repository and committing and pushing their changes via git commands.

¹² Markdown: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Markdown> [08.12.2021]

¹³ Programming Historians website: <https://programminghistorian.org/> [22.11.2021]

¹⁴ Sublime Text: <https://www.sublimetext.com/> [01.12.2021]

¹⁵ Atom: <https://atom.io/> [01.12.2021]

¹⁶ Notepad++: <https://notepad-plus-plus.org/> [01.12.2021]

¹⁷ NetlifyCMS: <https://www.netlifycms.org/> [22.11.2021]

The software is available for reuse under an open-source license in a public git repository¹⁸. The first installation of this system was done on DARIAH-Campus, a platform for the collaborative creation of training resources.

Main features include:

- git-based data storage and workflow;
- raw material easily available, because it is published via a git-based repository in a plain-text format (Markdown);
- additional metadata exposed through an API;
- structured metadata;
- rich-text editor;
- editorial workflow;
- support for grouping materials to form curricula or learning paths.

Fig 3: Screenshot of the editing interface of the new platform for authoring and publishing training material, featuring structured fields, rich-text-editor, git-based workflow, as well as on the fly preview

¹⁸ DARIAH-Campus git repository: <https://github.com/DARIAH-ERIC/dariah-campus> [01.12.2021]

5. Integration with Marketplace

From the onset of the project, a tight collaboration between task 6.3 and work package 7, aiming to develop the SSH Open Marketplace (MP), was foreseen. MP is a discovery platform for all kinds of resources relevant to the different stakeholders of the SSH community. Specifically, it aims to collect metadata about tools, services, publications, training materials, datasets and so-called workflows. One of the signature features of MP is contextualisation, i.e. an explicit linking of related entities, e.g. publications mentioning a tool or training material explaining the use of a service, or using a dataset as an example. This linking is done both through manual curation, as well as automated procedures. The automatic approach is mainly considered as an extraction task to identify mentions of tools in publications.

Information gathered in TDT represents an obvious input for the MP, while at the same time the MP is one of the major outcomes of the project with a clear strategy for long-term sustainability. This implies the necessity to consider the future fate of the outcomes of task 6.3, especially materialized in the TDT, in unison with that of the MP. At the same time, TDT has its dedicated role in the scope of the SSHOC Training community. The long-term fate of TDT remains yet to be decided.

Two possible scenarios are foreseen:

- a) TDT is kept and maintained as a separate application taken care of by partners in the pool of services resulting from the SSHOC project.
- b) Information from TDT is completely integrated into MP and serves as a dedicated view or sub-page of the MP, the original TDT application being shut down.

In both scenarios all the information from TDT should be integrated into MP by means of harvesting, a systematic procedure devised within WP7 for each of the sources populating the marketplace (see section 5.1). After the flow of information between TDT and MP has been established, there is some leeway as to the schedule of moving from scenario a) to scenario b), the two systems can coexist and share, i.e. synchronize the information. However, the major challenge in the long term is to keep the service running and especially the information up to date. In this respect it seems more efficient, to reduce the number of services that need to be curated and hosted. Thus, in the long-term, scenario b) seems more appropriate.

5.1 SSHOC training materials integration in the SSH Open Marketplace

The MP team has devised an elaborate approach to aggregate information from heterogeneous sources, through bespoke ingestion pipelines, governed by a custom-tailored mapping specific to the given

source. WP7 deliverables 7.2 *Marketplace Implementation* and 7.3 *Marketplace Interoperability*¹⁹ describe respectively the ingestion workflow and technical pipelines used, as well as the sources selected for ingestion

In general, the whole ingestion workflow can be summarised as follows: after selecting a source, a conceptual mapping between the metadata used by the source and the data model of the SSH Open Marketplace is first performed before being implemented via a custom pipeline and ingested in the MP system. One of the challenges in this exercise is to map the fields available in the source format to the fields of the MP data model. For example, the `title` field from TDT was mapped to the `label` field in the SSH Open Marketplace, `body` in TDT was mapped to `description`, and other specific properties were mapped one to one to dynamic properties in the Marketplace. The full process is described in detail in *D7.2 Marketplace Implementation*. Even though the MP data model is flexible and extensible, it still requires conceptual work to design an easily implementable mapping.

In the case of TDT, this challenge is simplified insofar as the source data model is under the control of the same team (DARIAH/OEAW) that created the MP data model, allowing for an informed decision in the mapping, or even adaptation of the data at the source, a luxury not available for most sources. Data from TDT are expected to be ingested in the SSH Open Marketplace by the end of 2021 or early 2022.

In the case of the training materials created during the SSHOC project or as part of the SSHOC events, one-time data ingestion towards the end of the project based on SSHOC website training events pages and harvesting the YouTube videos as well and the Zenodo slides is planned.

5.2 Training materials & Workflows in the Marketplace

SSH Open Marketplace, rather than being just another directory of tools or services, has an explicit focus on the “how”, i.e., the question of methodology. This is represented especially through two of the five main categories of information: training materials and workflows.

While training materials are represented as typical proxies via their metadata, i.e., the resource itself is hosted in a remote platform, workflows are considered a special entity, consisting of a sequence of steps stored in the marketplace.

It is worthwhile noting that one can discern a continuum ranging from typical learning resources as used in university curricula, training materials accompanying dedicated workshops, tutorials describing the use of a specific tool, down to workflows detailing a specific procedure. In the marketplace data model,

¹⁹ *D7.2 Marketplace Implementation*: Matej Ďurčo, Laure Barbot, Klaus Illmayer, Sotiris Karampatakis, Frank Fischer, Yoann Moranville, Joshua Tetteh Ocansey, Stefan Probst, Michał Kozak, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Seung-Bin Yim. (2021). 7.2 Marketplace – Implementation (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5749465> [08.12.2021],. *D7.3 Marketplace Interoperability* is being finalised at the time of writing.

the category training material is defined very broadly to encompass all of the above, with the exception of very specific descriptions of workflows.

Within the SSH Open Marketplace Editorial Guidelines²⁰, the following definitions are given for these two content types:

Training Material

a unique resource or ensemble of related resources explaining how to perform an action or highlighting the learning outcomes one would gain from engaging with the material

Examples: tutorials, lessons, user guides, handouts, videos, didactic resources.

Workflow

sequence of steps to describe a digital research method (comparable to 'recipes' in *methodi.ca*²¹ and 'scenarios' in the SSK²²)

Note: A workflow can be completed by using diverse tools and resources, connected to each step. As opposed to Training Materials, workflows are a series of steps (which can contain links to other resources) whereas the former are unique resources. Unlike other entries, Workflows can be hosted by the SSH Open Marketplace, and do not necessarily need to link to an external resource.

5.3 Continuous curation

To enhance discoverability and provide up-to-date and pertinent content to users, a continuous and collaborative curation workflow has been set in place for all Marketplace items, also applying to training materials. At the time of writing, the SSH Open Marketplace references 321 training materials²³. Thanks to the strong community-based approach to curation, these records can be updated or enriched by any logged-in user of the MP. These changes are subject to a review by a dedicated team of moderators. The curation process is detailed further below. In order to guarantee (meta)data quality of MP records, and depending on the type of items, recommended properties have been identified and described within MP Editorial Guidelines. These recommended metadata fields are flagged as a priority for the curation team, and their coverage (value presence in recommended fields) is one of the curation criteria used to

²⁰ These guidelines will be published as annex to D7.4 "Marketplace - data population & curation" as well as accessible on the final release of the SSH Open Marketplace (in Dec. 2021)

²¹ *methodi.ca*: <http://methodi.ca/> [25.11.2021]

²² Standardization Survival Kit: <http://ssk.huma-num.fr/> [25.11.2021]

²³ These training materials come from The Programming Historian, the SSK and the SSHOC catalogue. Data from the TDT and the SSHOC training events not being ingested yet.

continuously improve MP data quality. For training materials, the following fields are identified as recommended/important fields:

- label (is a mandatory field)
- description (is a mandatory field)
- actors
- accessibleAt
- externalIds
- media
- thumbnail
- relatedItems
- activity
- keyword
- discipline
- language
- object-format
- extent
- intended-audience
- see-also
- license
- terms-of-use-url
- year

One of these recommended fields, *relatedItems*, is particularly interesting as it allows the creation of relations between items in the Marketplace, providing context for a given resource through lateral connections, thus enhancing serendipity in the discovery of related resources. The typical case is training materials describing the use of specific tools or datasets (see Figure 3). However, given the flexible typing of the relations, it is also possible to connect several training materials forming a large unit, in the sense of a curriculum or learning path. This approach is already taken by at least two sources of the SSH Open Marketplace - The Programming Historian²⁴ and DARIAH-Campus²⁵ - and could be extended to other training materials in the SSH Open Marketplace.

²⁴ See the series of 15 lessons around Python in the Programming Historian starting with lesson1 Python Introduction and Installation - <https://programminghistorian.org/en/lessons/introduction-and-installation> [09.12.2021] - and ending with lesson 15 Downloading Multiple Records Using Query Strings - <https://programminghistorian.org/en/lessons/downloading-multiple-records-using-query-strings> [09.12.2021].

²⁵ See DARIAH-Campus curricula: <https://campus.dariah.eu/curricula/page/1> [09.12.2021]

Corpus Analysis with Antconc

[Go to Training material ↗](#)

Corpus analysis is a form of text analysis which allows you to make comparisons between textual objects at a large scale (so-called 'distant reading').

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Heather Froehlich

Source: [The Programming Historian](#)

DOI :[10.46430/phen0043](#)

GitHub :[programminghistorian/jekyll/blob/gh-pages/en/lessons/corpus-analysis-with-antconc.md](#)

INFORMATION CONTRIBUTORS
System importer
systemimporter@example.com

Fig 4: Example of a training material entry in the SSH Open marketplace - “Corpus Analysis with Antconc” from the Programming Historian source

Continuous curation of the SSH Open Marketplace is ensured by a mix of automated and manual tasks: some metrics have been extracted from quality criteria identified in the Editorial Guidelines, and a set of automated scripts (implemented as Python Jupyter notebooks) allow to regularly and systematically check the MP data and write back into the system to inform “curation-flags” available to Moderators²⁶ via the MP dashboard. Together with Administrators, Moderators form the Editorial Board which has the responsibility of reviewing suggestions from Contributors and improving MP data based on the curation-flags priorities. Details about the composition of the Editorial Team are provided in WP7 deliverables D7.5 “Marketplace governance” and D7.4 “Marketplace Data population & curation”. Given the (wide) scope of MP data content and of the sometimes technical operations needed to ensure data quality (vocabularies and actors curation is, for example, one of the tasks that falls into the Moderators and Administrators missions), members of the Editorial Board should possess a variety of complementary skills. In that sense, it is important to include in the Editorial Board persons familiar with TDT curation, aware of SSH researchers training scope and training materials needs (largely recruitable from the WP6 team), to ensure the quality of information about training materials in the SSH Open Marketplace.

²⁶ Three main roles are involved in the MP curation workflow: a Contributor is any logged in user who can only suggest content modification or creation; a Moderator reviews and accepts/rejects changes. An Administrator is not directly involved in the curation workflow but is the role with most rights; next to Moderator’s permissions they can also manage users and sources.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

The different lines of work performed by task 6.3 as described in this report have contributed to the SSHOC goal of collecting existing and supporting the creation of new training materials through a dedicated interface for the SSH communities.

A major challenge looking ahead is the question of keeping gathered information up to date. Only if the catalogue is continuously curated, both by reviewing the validity of the existing information and collecting new ones, will it remain a useful resource for the community. To this end, on the one hand, a dedicated application has been developed, which supports the maintenance of the information via a full-fledged CMS. On the other hand, a liaison with WP7 developing the SSH Open Marketplace has been sought, to ensure a coordinated approach with respect to long-term sustainability. Given the conceptual overlap, the plan devised for continuous curation of the Marketplace by the community and a dedicated editorial team, can also be applied for the catalogue of training materials. Part of the curation work will be also scouting for and harvesting new resources. This can be implemented by various means, as part of actions within follow-up projects, as dedicated curation workshops, or datathon, and especially also by coordinating with the RIs regarding the curation of their respective platforms and information outlets. In the long run, the TDT, as well as the training materials from the SSHOC project should become part of a continuously growing comprehensive set of SSH training resources.

Thus, following the current discussions around the strategy for long-term sustainability of SSHOC assets, T6.3 team recommends that these two services are in turn handled by the general plans of the RI-cluster involved in the project, whereby the local providers will collectively ensure further functioning of the main project outcomes under the framework of an agreement between the SSH ERICs.

These plans are related to the broader developments on the EOSC front, currently primarily as part of the EOSC-Future project²⁷, but also in some of the EOSC Association Task Forces²⁸ and EOSC-Future Working Groups²⁹, considering the integration of resources and research outputs generated and gathered by the cluster projects into a wider overarching EOSC catalogue. The inventorizing and curation work performed within the SSHOC project will naturally feed into these broader plans and initiatives, ensured by the strong presence of the RIs in these new efforts.

²⁷ EOSC-Future project website: <https://eoscfuture.eu/> [08.12.2021]

²⁸ EOSC Association Advisory Groups and Task Forces: <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups> [08.12.2021]

²⁹ EOSC-Future Working Groups: <https://eoscfuture.eu/eosc-future-working-groups/> [08.12.2021]

7. References

Matej Ďurčo, Laure Barbot, Klaus Illmayer, Sotiris Karampatakis, Frank Fischer, Yoann Moranville, Joshua Tetteh Ocansey, Stefan Probst, Michał Kozak, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Seung-Bin Yim. (2021). 7.2 Marketplace – Implementation (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5749465>

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